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*DEVELOPMENT OF YOUNG ENTREPRENEURSHIP WITH ITS
DIFFICULTIES AND STRATEGIES¹*

**DESENVOLVIMENTO DO EMPREENDEDORISMO JOVEM COM SUAS
DIFICULDADES E ESTRATÉGIAS**

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ABSTRACT

The study of entrepreneurship is crucial for the development of young entrepreneurs who seek to achieve independence through opening their own business. This study enables young people to identify opportunities and develop innovative ideas for the market. Therefore, this article discusses the topic of young entrepreneurship, and its problem is the following: what challenges does a young entrepreneur face in opening his own business in the tire industry, in the city of Navegantes – SC. To understand these challenges and strategies, the research was carried out using a qualitative approach, based on a case study and semi-structured interviews with the young entrepreneur. With the results of the interview, it is clear how important it is to strengthen the need for financial support and technical training in the daily lives of young people, so that an entrepreneurial culture can align with their personal and professional growth.

Keywords: young entrepreneurship, challenges of young entrepreneurship, entrepreneurship, young entrepreneurial culture.

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RESUMO

O estudo do empreendedorismo é crucial para o desenvolvimento de jovens empreendedores que buscam alcançar sua independência através da abertura de seu próprio negócio. Esse estudo capacita o jovem a identificar oportunidades e desenvolver ideias inovadoras para o mercado. Com isso o presente artigo discute o tema empreendedorismo jovem, e tem como a seguinte problemática: quais os desafios que um jovem empreendedor possui para abrir seu próprio negócio no ramo da borracharia, na cidade de Navegantes – SC. Para compreender esses desafios e estratégias, a pesquisa foi conduzida através de uma abordagem qualitativa, baseada em estudo de caso e entrevista semiestruturada com o jovem empreendedor. Com os resultados da entrevista, fica claro quão grande se torna a importância de reforçar a necessidade de suporte financeiro e de capacitação técnica no cotidiano dos jovens, para que a cultura empreendedora possa se alinhar em seu crescimento pessoal e profissional.

Palavras-chave: empreendedorismo jovem, desafios do empreendedorismo jovem, empreendedorismo, cultura empreendedora jovem.

INTRODUCTION

Sacramento (2023) observes the importance of entrepreneurship as a process of identifying opportunities and developing innovative ideas. The author also reflects that, due to the lack of opportunities in the labor market, some young people seek entrepreneurship as a solution to enter the business world, and may face several challenges when entering this environment; such difficulties can generate conflicts and insecurities for those who are just starting out.

According to Gomes et al. (2014), about 49% of new companies tend to close their doors within six years due to poor management and the lack of preparation of their entrepreneurs. Limited visibility regarding the need for strategic planning causes new entrepreneurs to lack market vision. This highlights the importance of analyzing the factors that influence young people's willingness to undertake entrepreneurship and seek autonomy by opening their own business.

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Brasil et al. (2013) question the circumstances that may influence the practice of entrepreneurship, such as social, economic, and cultural conditions. They also point out that the reasons that may interfere with the decisions, behaviors, and attitudes of young entrepreneurs are significant for understanding their motivations and for comprehending the course of business development.

Filho et al. (2009) comment that most young people do not have access to education on proper ways to undertake entrepreneurship. The author also reflects on the need for basic knowledge linked to financial planning, enabling better future conditions. According to Bulgacov et al. (2011), in Brazil, however, the culture of entrepreneurship is not frequently addressed or taught to young people.

Following this perspective, Filho et al. (2009) states that it is necessary to show the youth community, together with the country's economic sectors, that there are other opportunities for economic inclusion for everyone, making it possible to break the belief that only formal jobs constitute a professional career. For Brasil et al. (2013), consequently, entrepreneurship is presented as an alternative professional path, especially for the youth community, contributing to the achievement of new opportunities, both professional and personal.

The difficulties related to the need for knowledge about entrepreneurship cause many companies to decline in a short time. Given this reality, combined with the challenges of youth entrepreneurship in the country, negative aspects can be observed that need to be addressed. In this context, the present research poses the following research problem: what challenges does a young entrepreneur face when opening their own tire repair business in the city of Navegantes, Santa Catarina?

The general objective of this research is to understand the challenges and strategies of youth entrepreneurship in a tire repair shop in the region of Navegantes. The specific objectives of the study are: (i) to identify how

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entrepreneurship is perceived by the young entrepreneur; (ii) to describe the reality of a young entrepreneur in the tire repair sector, considering their knowledge and difficulties; and (iii) to analyze tools that enable a young entrepreneur in the tire repair sector to achieve better organizational development within their workplace.

This work was developed with the aim of answering these questions and conveying the importance of entrepreneurship to young people and its characteristics, highlighting its overall relevance to the business world and to youth socioeconomic culture. It is hypothesized that entrepreneurship suffers from a lack of discussion on the topic, which is often not addressed to the youth audience, despite being an important aspect of their financial independence. A second hypothesis is that the reality of young entrepreneurs in the tire repair sector is marked by significant difficulties, such as the lack of specific technical and managerial knowledge, which compromises operational efficiency and business sustainability.

THEORETICAL FOUNDATION/LITERATURE REVIEW

The need for academic research is evident, as discussed in Lakatos's (2003) study, which observes that many young people seek to develop businesses, but these businesses face difficulties due to a lack of effective knowledge. Understanding entrepreneurship and conceptualizing it effectively is crucial for developing a quality strategic and financial plan for the initial years of a new company.

Entrepreneurship in Brazil

Dornelas (2005) understands that entrepreneurship in Brazil is considered fundamental for the country's economic growth; however, before addressing the topic and its role, it is necessary to discuss the concept of

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entrepreneurship. The author also notes its French origin: the word entrepreneur refers to someone who takes risks and starts something new.

Cunha (2004) further explains that, throughout history, the term derives from the Latin *imprehendere*, meaning “one who proposes to try and puts into practice.” For Baron and Shane (2007), definitions can be tricky, especially when discussing a topic such as entrepreneurship, for which there is no clear consensus, since its field may refer both to the study of business and to an activity in which people engage. Even with its various definitions, entrepreneurship is most commonly conceptualized as the act of undertaking, characterized by processes of innovation and discovery (Boava and Macedo, 2009).

Schumpeter (1988) observes that opportunities stimulate the creation of businesses, which in turn generate economic development for the country. Meanwhile, Fialho et al. (2006) state that entrepreneurship can be understood as a process occurring in different places and business contexts, capable of leading organizations to produce significant changes in society. Thus, it is evident that entrepreneurs feel motivated to seek new opportunities and recognize them as a starting point for undertaking ventures (GEM, 2014).

According to Dornelas (2005), entrepreneurship in Brazil already had a certain level of popularity, but it gained greater prominence in the mid-1990s when organizations emerged with the purpose of guiding those who sought to develop as entrepreneurs. In Brazil, companies play a crucial and highly visible role in economic growth, being responsible for driving innovation, promoting national development, increasing the country’s Gross Domestic Product (GDP), generating thousands of jobs, contributing to income generation, and enhancing the country’s national and international recognition (Baggio and Baggio, 2014).

With a growing number of unemployed individuals seeking solutions to leave this condition, many chose entrepreneurship as a source of income (Oliveira, 1995). In Brazilian industry, research and data show that a large part of

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the population seeks to open their own business in search of financial independence. According to data from Brazil (2023), by August 2023, 2,716,269 companies had been registered as newly opened, with around 21.8 million active businesses, of which 93.7% were microenterprises or small businesses. While 2.7 million companies were opened, 1.47 million closed; however, the balance by August 2023 remained positive, with 1.23 million businesses opened.

Microenterprises and small businesses were created to help move many people out of informality. Through Complementary Law No. 128 of December 19, 2008, the legal category of the Individual Microentrepreneur (MEI) was established, bringing many benefits that allow the population to begin entrepreneurial activities with important rights and reduced taxes (Legg, 2020). Nevertheless, part of this population that opens small businesses faces difficulties in keeping them operating.

According to a study conducted by Sebrae based on RFB databases and field research carried out between 2018 and 2021, individual microentrepreneurs (MEIs) have the highest mortality rate among small businesses, with 29% closing after five years of activity. Microenterprises (MEs) have an intermediate mortality rate, with 21.6% closing after five years, while small companies (EPPs) have the lowest rate, with 17% closing after five years (SEBRAE, 2023).

Even with the many obstacles faced by entrepreneurs in the business world, it is still possible for companies to succeed and survive. In addition to the merit of visionary thinking and the dedication of entrepreneurs, there is support from organizations that help professionalize them further. SEBRAE (Brazilian Support Service for Micro and Small Enterprises) is one of the institutions that provides assistance and support to entrepreneurs (Maximiano, 2006).

According to Dornelas (2005), entrepreneurship may have different determinants in its initiation. One is necessity-driven entrepreneurship, in which individuals seek alternatives to overcome financial scarcity and reestablish themselves in the market, often characterized by a lack of planning and

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organization and vulnerability to future losses. According to a GEM (2017) survey, about 39.9% of entrepreneurs opened new businesses out of necessity without adequate planning and therefore risk not achieving long-term success.

However, according to Bandeira and Silva (2023), the fact that entrepreneurs start businesses out of necessity may be associated with developing countries; for this reason, they tend to overcome difficulties and pursue more creative and innovative ventures to face economic challenges.

Opportunity-driven entrepreneurship, on the other hand, allows businesses to develop more fluidly, as they are based on proper planning and a visionary outlook for a solid future in the market (Dornelas, 2005). According to the author, undertaking a venture by opportunity means choosing to open a business with a focus on strategic growth and success, rather than seeking a quick solution to unemployment or lack of income. According to GEM (2020), the rate of opportunity-driven entrepreneurship in Brazil was 12.6% in 2020, higher than the previous year, which reached 11.1%.

Bandeira and Silva (2023) agree that, to undertake entrepreneurship, it is necessary to seek and develop specific skills that allow entrepreneurs to plan and improve in order to maintain their business solid and functioning in the long term. Thus, according to Machado (2005), education contributes to an entrepreneurial culture aimed at fostering the development of future small businesses. In turn, for the development of entrepreneurship in society to succeed, it is necessary to create government policies that address specific challenges so that future entrepreneurs can achieve success throughout their ventures.

Profile of the young entrepreneur

The involvement of young people in entrepreneurship occurs for various reasons; in today's market, they increasingly seek to engage in running their own

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businesses, intrinsically associating entrepreneurship with innovation, resilience, and the business environment (Machado, 2005). Brazil is considered a demographically young country, and as youth transition into adulthood, a shift in social status takes place (Dornelas, 2008). According to Bulgacov et al. (2011), young Brazilian entrepreneurs seek business opportunities and creative solutions to meet market demands, while facing challenges such as bureaucracy and lack of financial resources.

For McClelland (1972), the perception of entrepreneurship in the psychological sphere relates to the need for achievement, acting as a driving force behind entrepreneurial behavior and resulting in economic progress. The author also reflects that understanding young people's motivation to undertake entrepreneurship requires characterizing their life context and how this motivation can be transformed into ideas to create and develop their own business. According to Kristiansen and Indarti (2004), an individual's personality constantly changes, especially when considering external environments, both in local and global society.

Carvalho et al. (2012) argue that political actions are necessary due to the harmful effects that youth unemployment can generate for societal well-being. According to the authors, those seeking employment (aged 16 to 35) view entrepreneurship positively, yet few actually pursue this career path. They also note that, regardless of financial difficulties in starting a business, the most dominant obstacle reported by young people is the lack of essential technical knowledge and managerial training, pointing to a deficiency in entrepreneurial education.

In this context, entrepreneurial education is a necessary component, since managerial and leadership skills develop through practice. Learning through mentorship and techniques contributes to both personal and professional maturity when starting a business. The need for continuous improvement and

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knowledge shapes an organization regardless of its niche or sector (Bulgacov et al., 2011).

Santos and Gonçalves (2020) analyze that one existing option to overcome unemployment is self-employment. They argue that young people seek a favorable environment to build and develop their business ideas and innovations, focusing on continuous learning and rapid adaptation. They also note that owning a business is the desire of 44% of Brazilians, according to surveys, which show greater interest in entrepreneurship than in formal employment.

Carvalho et al. (2012) reported in their study that data presented in Brazil showed that since 2011, around 27 million people aged between 18 and 64 were managers or owners of some type of business, regardless of size or time of establishment. However, a decline was observed from 17.5% to 14.89% in early-stage entrepreneurs among young businesspeople aged 18 to 34. They also suggest that one explanation for this decline is the increasing demand for qualified labor.

However, Ribeiro and Teixeira (2012) state that many young people see entrepreneurship as an opportunity to fulfill their dreams and achieve personal and professional fulfillment that may not be found in traditional jobs. Although such achievements bring challenges, they also lead to many accomplishments. The authors further observe that the initial motivations for entrepreneurship vary, but the main ones stem from business opportunities, financial independence, and personal fulfillment.

Thus, entrepreneurship is considered an agent of economic development, job creation, and social stability; worldwide, it plays an important role in the progress of countries (Carvalho et al., 2012). In this way, entrepreneurs stimulate the economy by providing new products for consumption and innovating production (Ribeiro and Teixeira, 2012).

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Difficulties in business management

The process of developing an organization requires effort at the moment of its creation, when a new venture is launched. It is necessary to analyze every detail regarding the expectations and goals intended for the new business, so that a functional action plan can be developed to ensure success in business management. A focus on strategic planning and financial planning provides the starting point for an organization with stronger financial health (Bernardi, 2008).

According to Sacramento (2023), organizations - especially those just entering the market - face a series of challenges. Some of these include adaptation: for a company to remain strong, it must continuously adapt to the market and align itself with the needs of its target audience. Another challenge is lack of experience, which can lead to poor management and incorrect decision-making within the company. The lack of formal study or preparation among beginners can also be considered one of the main challenges young entrepreneurs face in maintaining the longevity of their business.

Ribeiro and Teixeira (2012) state that innovation is also a challenge, since organizations must remain attentive to the market in order to develop updated management practices for their audience. They further argue that a lack of financial resources limits young people from undertaking entrepreneurial activities, as investment requires some level of financial capacity to expand an idea. A lack of contacts and market competition are also included among the challenges and needs young people must face in managing their new ventures.

According to Dornelas (2008), implementing management practices is essential for developing solutions and meeting the needs that arise at the beginning and throughout the process of establishing an organization. The author also emphasizes that business management is highly important for organizational development, as it seeks improvements in performance and structure. This reality

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encompasses activities and processes that coordinate and control resources in order to achieve and optimize the company's objectives.

Business management encompasses several areas, including planning, organization, leadership, and control; these areas aim to ensure effective management of a venture (Fayol, 1994). In addition to building components that support company growth, business management plays a significant role in creating strategic processes within the workplace, positively impacting managerial improvements (Henrique, 2021).

Many young entrepreneurs tend to have difficulty understanding how to proceed with their ventures. According to Dolabela (1999), the lack of entrepreneurial education among youth creates a knowledge gap for those who are thinking about or beginning to undertake entrepreneurship. For Gomes et al. (2014), entrepreneurial education is crucial for youth development, as it not only prepares them for the course of business life but also contributes to the gradual formation of successful young entrepreneurs.

Lizote et al. (2020) add that young people need to seek and understand the importance of organizational processes in shaping how companies operate. Therefore, it is essential that they learn not only financial, operational, and marketing techniques, but also develop an understanding of their interpersonal skills. In this sense, Reina and Santos (2017) note that young people's understanding of business development comes from education; thus, this type of education must be incorporated into the learning of children and youth so that, when they consider opening their future ventures, they possess the necessary knowledge to begin and achieve organizational success.

METHODOLOGICAL PROCEDURES

For the development of this research, a basic research approach was chosen. Basic research refers to a type of approach that aims to understand a

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given subject but is not necessarily linked to a practical application (Prodanov, 2013).

The research is characterized by a qualitative approach, seeking to answer questions related to youth entrepreneurship, understand the development of a small business, and identify the experiences and challenges encountered along this path. According to Santos and Gonçalves (2020), this research model seeks to understand the experiences people go through in certain situations within the social world. Thus, qualitative research is conducted through investigation to understand and respond to a particular social issue (Rodrigues, 2021).

The research was carried out through a case study in a company located in Navegantes, Santa Catarina, based on an interview with the young entrepreneur who owns the business. He is 24 years old and began his professional life in the field at a very early age, approximately at 16 years old. The interview was conducted in person at his tire repair shop.

The materials required for data collection included a recorder to capture the entire conversation with the interviewee and a notebook to document and describe the interview. An open (semi-structured) interview format was used, allowing interesting points to emerge during the conversation through the questions posed to the interviewee. The research aims to be descriptive, as it seeks to understand and describe what will be studied during the process and its real characteristics (Gil, 2002). In other words, this type of research provides knowledge to the researcher about the field studied and its reality, without interference.

Regarding the technical procedure adopted, a case study method was used, which seeks to portray a specific subject or aspect of society. According to Gil (2002), this procedure consists of studying a subject in order to clarify doubts

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and highlight issues that have not yet been fully answered, thereby generating a broader understanding of the research and helping to clarify the topic studied.

The analysis and interpretation of the data will be conducted through content analysis, which, according to Severino (2002), is a methodology that examines information present in documents and texts and seeks to interpret and understand communications by analyzing their content in search of meaning. These contents may consist of oral, written, visual, figurative, or documentary materials, leading to a deeper or different understanding of the researched topic.

ANALYSIS AND INTERPRETATION OF RESULTS

The overall objective of the research was to understand the challenges of entrepreneurship in a tire repair shop, to assess the importance of youth entrepreneurship, and to point out the challenges for entrepreneurship in the segment and in the region.

During the interview, the interviewee recounted how this entrepreneurial process unfolded, and how this pursuit of independence brought opportunities and challenges throughout their journey as a young entrepreneur.

Perceptions about entrepreneurship

The topic of entrepreneurship is widely discussed across different age groups and cultures, emerging from the expectation of starting a business and owning one's own venture. For young people, its relevance is extremely important when thinking about developing their professional lives and autonomy, and they are increasingly seeking ideas and solutions to develop their projects (Sacramento, 2023).

When putting their ideas into practice, certain difficulties and opportunities become evident throughout the process. Therefore, this research

sought to report how this experience unfolded for an entrepreneur in the tire repair sector. In Chart 1, the interview report is presented:

Questions	Respondent
<p>1. How do you perceive the role of entrepreneurship among young people in your region?</p>	<p>In Navegantes, I see that there isn't much young entrepreneurship; it's as if people are afraid to start their own business, whether because they're new, don't feel capable, or lack experience. When visiting establishments, it's noticeable that the owners are mostly older. In my view, young people aren't taking the plunge and wanting to start their own businesses; in other words, here in Navegantes, young people don't have much of that entrepreneurial culture, from what I've seen in my years living here. But I believe it's very important to have that culture, that role, especially starting to undertake a business from a young age; we have a responsibility to carry forward that responsibility.</p>
<p>2. What are the main incentives or challenges you faced when starting your own business?</p>	<p>My first encouragement came from my father, who always wanted us to run our own business. Since he already worked in the tire repair business, he chose for us to follow the same path, as it was a good area to work in because he already had experience. And so we started in the tire repair business. The challenge was that I had a regular job and was afraid to leave, since I already had a fixed salary at the company. And when you open your own business, you don't know if it will start well in the first few months, if it will succeed or not, leaving your regular job without any certainty of success is a bad idea.</p>
<p>3. How do you see the acceptance and support of the local community for youth entrepreneurship?</p>	<p>I realized they embraced the idea because I'm a new guy; they kind of encouraged me since most people my age don't want to work in the job I do, because it's physically demanding. So they were very supportive; it's just a matter of prioritizing customer service and working with the care and attention that I give, and I'll prosper.</p>

4. Do you think young entrepreneurs have sufficient access to resources (financial, educational, etc.) to start a business?	I think it will depend on the business. In the field I work in, which is tire repair, it's difficult. The financial help I had came from my father; he already had capital to invest in me, to get me started. And regarding educational support, he was the one who taught me, since in my area, whether you like it or not, you don't need a specific course; you just need to work with someone who already has a lot of experience in this area. This educational and financial support came solely from my father. So, if these young people who want to start in this field don't have a way to generate income to start their own business, it will become much more difficult to begin, because the government or other organizations will hardly provide that initial money. Besides, they wouldn't have the experience, unless they work in a tire repair shop for a long time and, in that time, save some money if they can, so that when they try to open their own tire repair shop they can succeed.
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Chart 1: Identifying how entrepreneurship is perceived by young entrepreneurs
Source: elaborated by the authors (2024)

In question number 1, regarding the role of entrepreneurship among young people in his region, the respondent stated that in his city there is little evidence of a culture of young entrepreneurs, whether due to fear or unwillingness to enter the business world. At the same time, he recognizes how important this culture is for young people to cultivate responsibility among themselves. According to Machado (2005), in recent years the entrepreneurial culture has gained strength, leading educational institutions to develop processes aligned with what young people are seeking. However, due to current economic crises and high unemployment rates, many young people pursue this path on their own, which can generate frustration, since entering the business world without adequate training can become disastrous. Failure rates show that companies opened without proper knowledge of what is required to operate in their field tend to close too early.

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Varela (1991) adds that, with this growing demand and the current crisis scenario, young people increasingly seek education and training, and educational institutions need to adapt quickly to this changing environment in order to support the development and advancement of entrepreneurial education and culture among youth. Some studies indicate that the entrepreneurial spirit can be enhanced through education, increasing the chances of successfully creating, establishing, and advancing entrepreneurial careers and effectively achieving their goals.

In question 2, about the main incentives or challenges he faced when starting his own business, the respondent summarized that his greatest encouragement came from his father, who helped him throughout the entire process of opening the business. His main difficulty was leaving the security of a stable job to open the tire repair shop without any guarantee of success. According to Dolabela (1999), family support is crucial—not only financial support, but also encouragement and motivation that help reduce the fear of failure. With his father's support, the respondent felt protected during the company's start-up phase, which was essential for achieving the expected results. However, the challenge of giving up job stability remained a major concern.

Dolabela (1999) further explains that the fear of leaving stability for a new and uncertain world is common among young people who consider starting their own business. Nevertheless, opening a new venture requires courage to deal with uncertainties and the ability to manage financial risks that arise along the way, which are often offset by the independence and personal satisfaction provided by the new project. These decisions reflect a willingness to change and to take on a leading role in seeking financial security, autonomy, and personal and professional growth.

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Question 3 asked the interviewee how he perceives the acceptance and support of the local community toward youth entrepreneurship. He responded that the support from the local community was notable, with encouragement from people who admired the fact that he was young and already seeking financial independence, as well as the care he demonstrated in his work and his way of communicating with clients. According to Matos et al. (2007), community support is one of the elements that most strongly influences the initial success of young entrepreneurs, as it promotes persistence and strengthens the business—especially when the entrepreneur demonstrates skill, attentiveness, and effective communication with clients, thereby building trust. Being well received by the community has helped motivate him to continue progressing and consolidating his business.

Finally, in question 4, the interviewee was asked whether he believes young entrepreneurs have sufficient access to resources (financial, educational, etc.) to start a business. In his view, within the sector in which he operates, obtaining financial support is not easy. His main support came from his father, who already had capital to invest in the business. He also advised young people who wish to enter this field to plan carefully and first specialize by working in a tire repair shop alongside experienced professionals, and to save money to purchase the necessary materials to get started, as there are no specific institutions that provide financial support for this sector.

In the same vein, Reis and Santos (2021) note that entrepreneurs face major challenges when attempting to start and sustain their own businesses due to the bureaucratic demands involved in the process. Planning and securing resources during the start-up phase are essential to prevent the business from closing prematurely. In other words, to deal with these challenges, it is crucial to ensure financial stability and have adequate planning.

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Knowledge and the challenges of entrepreneurship

Lack of experience or access to specific knowledge in the field in which they wish to work becomes a difficulty in the life of a young entrepreneur who dreams of—or often needs—having their own source of income. According to Gomes et al. (2014), there is a need for more entrepreneurial education in the lives of young people who seek to pursue their own businesses. It is necessary to develop new forms of teaching and learning to prepare young people not to rely solely on the idea of conventional employment, but to adopt innovative and entrepreneurial behaviors.

In Chart 2, the second section of the interview will be presented, which seeks to understand the knowledge, experiences, and difficulties that young entrepreneurs go through—or will go through—when starting their own businesses.

In question 1 of the second section of the interview, which addressed the main difficulties the entrepreneur encountered when starting a tire repair shop, the interviewee reported that his primary difficulty was the shop's location. It is situated in a remote area, making it harder for people to find it or even know that it operates there. According to Sebrae (2022), the location of a business establishment is important for generating customer flow, as the commercial location directly impacts the success of the venture. However, after the tire repair shop opened and customers appreciated the quality of the service provided, word-of-mouth promotion helped the location become known and quickly recognized.

The interviewee also mentioned another factor he considered a challenge at the beginning: his age, which is relatively young for starting a business in this field. He noted that customers were initially somewhat hesitant due to his youth, questioning whether he would perform the service properly.

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However, over time, as they observed the quality of his work, they began to trust him and appreciate his services (Sebrae, 2022).

Questions	Respondent
1. What were the main difficulties you encountered when starting a tire repair shop?	One of the difficulties I see is the location of the tire shop; being behind a gas station, somewhat set back, people don't know there's a tire shop there. A few years ago there was a tire shop there, but it was closed for a long time, so it took a while to spread the word that a new one had opened. Another point I see is that, because of my age, being young, people would come in for repairs and see a young guy and wonder if it would be a good job, but then they saw that I did a good job and they gained more confidence.
2. How did your prior knowledge (in administration, finance, mechanics, etc.) influence the management of your business?	I don't consider myself very experienced in this area; I know the basics, like opening my MEI (Individual Microentrepreneur) by watching videos online, and paying my DAIs (Simplified Tax Collection Documents), which is very important for MEIs to know because if they aren't paid, it's dangerous to accumulate a huge debt and end up closing down. In the beginning, I had no idea about the administrative side, but I knew I needed to handle the rent. However, over time I've organized that part. I know how to manage income and expenses, and what needs to be paid, but I'm not the right person to handle the administrative and financial aspects. My wife takes care of that part more, and we plan to hire an accountant in the future since we intend to change the company's business category.
3. Do you believe that lack of experience can be a barrier for young entrepreneurs in this field?	It's definitely a significant barrier, because knowing how to handle this type of work is important to prevent accidents, and if the person doesn't have experience in the field, they might even drive customers away. When I opened my tire shop, I already had experience, which is what allowed me to build a good clientele. If you start working for yourself, you need to have that experience, especially with very manual work that requires attention. And if you open it haphazardly, it won't work; you need to have that understanding, otherwise the business won't thrive. So yes, it's very important to have that knowledge and experience in the field for the business to succeed.
4. What skills or knowledge do you consider essential for successfully managing a tire repair shop?	Agility, I think, is essential in my line of work. You have to be fast, do a good job, and provide good customer service. We know there are ignorant customers and there are more cheerful ones; you have to know how to deal with each one, you have to have dialogue, know how to handle customers. Sometimes they arrive a bit rude and stressed, but you have to know how to act calmly and not complain about the service. Another thing is having the willingness to work, since it's not an easy job, so you need stamina. And skill with the equipment is essential, like using a hydraulic air jack, a pneumatic tool.

Chart 2: The reality of a young entrepreneur considering their knowledge and difficulties.
Source: elaborated by the authors (2024)

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In question 2, the interviewee was asked how his prior knowledge in administration, finance, mechanics, and related areas influenced the management of his business. He commented that he had little knowledge in administration and finance, and what he did know he learned by watching videos on the internet, which did not make him experienced in this aspect of the business. Regarding bureaucratic matters, he handled everything independently. According to Dornelas (2005), teaching entrepreneurship is not easy, as most entrepreneurs seek to start autonomously and make things happen on their own. Therefore, educators and public institutions need to provide practical learning environments that use real examples. Although entrepreneurial education does not guarantee the emergence of great entrepreneurs, it helps prepare those who seek to identify skills, opportunities, innovation, and business management.

Question 3 asked whether the interviewee believes that lack of experience can be a barrier for young entrepreneurs in this field. In his view, it is very important that young people who want to start in this area have experience, especially in the tire repair sector, which requires solid practical knowledge because it is highly manual work that demands care and precision. Lack of experience represents an obstacle for young entrepreneurs, as without technical and practical skills they may face difficulties in managing the business. According to Reis and Santos (2021), experience in the field is essential for business success, and inexperience can limit a young entrepreneur's ability to perform their work effectively.

Finally, in question 4 of the second section, the interviewee highlighted the skills and knowledge he considers essential for managing a successful tire repair shop. In his opinion, agility and high-quality workmanship are fundamental in this field. He also emphasized the importance of maintaining good relationships with customers and knowing how to deal with each individual, even in stressful situations. Another point he stressed is the need for physical readiness to work

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in this sector, as it involves demanding tasks and the use of heavy equipment, which must also be handled properly.

Tools for improved organizational development

In the context of youth entrepreneurship, the use of appropriate tools and technologies is fundamental to improving processes and ensuring the viability of the venture, guaranteeing business efficiency. The adoption of management practices and the use of technological resources are essential for organizational progress and the continued longevity of companies (Dornelas, 2008).

Next, the last topic of the interview will be presented, which seeks to understand what tools can be used to improve the organizational development of ventures.

Questions	Respondent
1. What tools or technologies do you use to manage your tire shop?	I believe the best invention for my field has been pneumatic machines, which allow us to remove screws and nuts more efficiently and quickly. There's also the compressor, without which it's impossible to work, hydraulic air jacks, and tire changers; all these tools are essential for fast and efficient work in a tire shop. And in terms of technology, whether you like it or not, you have to have internet, which is used for everything, and I mainly use it for invoicing and to take care of the administrative side of the tire shop, along with a computer to keep track of this in a more practical way.
2. How would you rate the effectiveness of these tools in your daily work?	I rate it excellently, of course, if the correct period for preventive maintenance is followed, because without these tools the service would become very difficult.
3. Do you feel the need for more training or skills development to improve your use of these tools?	From my point of view, I don't need more training; I'm proficient with the tools I have. However, since I'm planning to acquire an automatic truck tire dismantling machine, then yes, I will need more training and skills development. But apart from that, I'm already qualified for my job.

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<p>4. What types of organizational support (such as consulting, training, etc.) do you consider most useful for the growth of your business?</p>	<p>Today, the main support I see needed for a tire shop is partnerships with companies that resell tires. I believe that would be one of the things that would boost the tire shop. Another thing is having an accounting firm to manage the business. As I intend to move to the next level, today I'm a self-employed individual (MEI), so as I intend to grow to a micro-enterprise and hire people, having an accounting firm to manage this process would be essential.</p>
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Chart 3: Tools that enable better organizational development:
Source: elaborated the authors (2024)

In question 1, the interviewee was asked which tools or technologies he uses to manage his tire repair shop. In his response, he emphasized the importance of these tools in his daily work, such as pneumatic machines for the quick and efficient removal of bolts and nuts, which streamline the process and optimize service time. Beyond the tools used during service, he also highlighted the importance of the internet and the computer he uses for managing the business. According to Jackson (2022), tools and technologies are important for increasing service efficiency and flexibility, enabling workers to perform tasks more quickly and accurately, resulting in higher productivity.

In question 2, regarding the effectiveness of these tools in his daily routine, the interviewee assessed that his practical use of the tools in the tire repair shop is excellent. He stressed that these tools must be properly maintained for work to run smoothly, since without them the services would be much more complex and time-consuming. According to Moreira and Marcheti (2017), the operational efficiency of some small businesses depends on the quality and maintenance of the tools used, as poorly maintained equipment can directly affect productivity and service quality. Proper maintenance is therefore crucial for the entrepreneur's success.

Question 3 asked whether he feels the need for further training or qualification to improve the use of these tools. He stated that, with the tools he currently has, he does not feel the need for additional training, as he considers himself capable of using them correctly. However, he acknowledged that he

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intends to acquire an automatic machine for dismounting truck tires, which will require additional training to operate. According to Colombo (2021), proper training improves skills, increases efficiency and safety in the use of complex equipment, enhances service performance, and raises the professional's level of expertise, helping elevate the business to a higher level.

Finally, in the closing question of the interview, he was asked what types of organizational support he considers most useful for the growth of his business. In response, the interviewee identified two forms of support he considers necessary for the expansion of his tire repair shop. One is partnerships with companies that resell tires, which could boost the business and attract new customers. The other is hiring an accounting service, since his plan is to expand his business from an individual microentrepreneur (MEI) to a microenterprise, and accounting will be essential in this process. According to SEBRAE (2024), partnerships are highly relevant to business development, as such collaborations can play a strategic role in expanding networks and attracting new consumers. These partnerships may elevate the company to another level, making effective accounting management necessary, as it supports financial organization and helps ensure compliance with legal obligations while improving the company's fiscal structure, providing a safer environment for business development (Oliveira et al., 2022).

FINAL CONSIDERATIONS

This article discussed the topic of youth entrepreneurship and sought to understand the difficulties and strategies faced by a young entrepreneur when starting a tire repair business. The research was guided by and aimed to answer the problem question: What challenges does a young entrepreneur face in opening and sustaining a tire repair business? The question was addressed through a case study involving a semi-structured interview with a young

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entrepreneur in the sector. During the conversation, it was discussed that the main difficulties young entrepreneurs face when starting their ventures include a lack of experience and technical knowledge, difficulty obtaining financial resources to start the business, fear of failure when exploring something new, and the lack of an entrepreneurial culture that supports young people from an early age in considering owning their own business in the region.

By maintaining a more critical perspective throughout the study, the need for greater incentives in the pursuit of financial independence became evident, as well as how the absence of financial, family, and educational support hinders the development of entrepreneurial ideas. Thus, to address the general objective, a semi-structured interview was conducted in which, through detailed questions, the main obstacles and strategies experienced and employed by the entrepreneur during this process were presented. Regarding the specific objectives, expectations for obtaining answers were also met: (i) by identifying how entrepreneurship is perceived by the young entrepreneur, the relevance of the topic was recognized, as well as how the absence of incentives for young people can discourage them from achieving independence and pursuing their dreams; (ii) by describing the reality of young entrepreneurs in the tire repair sector, practical knowledge and the difficulties faced during the business start-up process were considered; (iii) by analyzing the tools that enable the organizational development of young entrepreneurs in the sector, practices and tools that improve performance and the functioning of the tire repair shop were explored.

Two hypotheses were developed in this research. The first suggested that entrepreneurship suffers from a lack of attention as a topic that is often not addressed to young audiences as an important pathway to financial freedom. This hypothesis was confirmed, as the study reveals that young people still view entrepreneurship with some apprehension due to the financial and cultural

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challenges they would face when putting a business into practice. This leads to hesitation in considering entrepreneurship as a viable path to financial independence, and throughout the research it is shown how this process can be complex and difficult for some individuals.

The second hypothesis proposed that the reality of young entrepreneurs in the tire repair sector is marked by significant difficulties, such as a lack of specific technical and managerial knowledge, which compromises operational efficiency and business sustainability. This was also confirmed, as the interviewee reported the challenges that may arise for those wishing to follow the same path and how the absence of managerial knowledge can directly affect the operation of the business. He also reported facing some difficulties himself; however, with the financial and emotional support he received from his family, the process became smoother. Nevertheless, this is not the reality for everyone, which can generate substantial challenges.

In terms of achieving the study's objectives, this article fulfilled its purpose of providing an understanding of the challenges faced by a young tire repair entrepreneur, highlighting the need for training programs and support for youth entrepreneurship so that they can access more resources and skills for their businesses. From a scientific perspective, the research enriches the field of entrepreneurship by demonstrating its importance for education and by highlighting the negative impact that the absence of incentives and educational support has on young entrepreneurs, especially in technical fields such as tire repair. It also emphasizes the relevance of public policies and educational programs focused on developing managerial skills from a young age, aiming to strengthen and reduce early failure rates among new ventures.

The study presents some limitations that restrict and complicate the collection of results. The focus on a single sector - the tire repair industry - and on a single interviewee makes it difficult to compare experiences among

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entrepreneurs in this field. Another limitation is the scarcity of articles addressing this research topic in sectors such as tire repair, which makes it difficult to access materials that could support the study. Therefore, future research is recommended to expand the sample, focusing not only on young people in the tire repair sector but also including other technical areas, such as mechanics, to allow comparisons between different realities and the strategies used to maintain business operations. Another important topic to investigate would be the relevance of training programs and financial support and their impact on the lives of young entrepreneurs, aiming to establish foundations for public policies that encourage and sustain youth entrepreneurship in Brazil.

Therefore, the study shows that despite the difficulties faced, the environment of youth entrepreneurship can be strengthened through joint initiatives among individuals, families, and institutions, as promoting this culture requires a collective effort. Investing in young people and their education is crucial for developing capable entrepreneurs who contribute to the country's economic development and who can achieve their dreams and goals while sustaining their businesses.

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